

Research Report

Investigating plasticity of the olfactory system through the lens of specific anosmia

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ABSTRACT

The olfactory experiences vary widely among individuals. Despite having an otherwise normal sense of smell, some people exhibit specific anosmia, i.e., the inability to detect certain odorants. While genetic factors play a key role in this phenomenon, olfactory perception is also influenced by environment, and repeated exposure to odors (olfactory training) can enhance olfactory sensitivity. In this study, we examined whether olfactory training increases sensitivity towards odors participants were specifically anosmic to, and preliminarily investigated whether this training-induced change is stable over time. Initially, we screened 335 participants with healthy sense of smell to identify individuals with specific anosmia towards androstenone, benzyl salicylate, bacdanol, or maltol. Subsequently, 77 participants with at least one specific anosmia underwent 2-months long olfactory training with these four odorants. We observed that following the training, participants became more sensitive towards odors they were specifically anosmic to, whereas sensitivity towards odors they were able to perceive at baseline did not change. However, the effects of olfactory training on specific anosmia were transient – 19 months after the training completion, 9 out of 10 followed-up participants became specifically anosmic towards androstenone again. Altogether, our findings demonstrate that the human olfactory system adjusts to novel odorous inputs, but these environmentally driven changes do not appear to be permanent in healthy participants.

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1. Introduction

The world smells different for each one of us. When we breathe, odorous molecules reach the olfactory epithelium and bind to olfactory receptor neurons which initiates the process of olfactory processing and eventually evokes a conscious percept of smell (Freiherr, 2017; Zhao et al., 2004). However, whether an odor is perceived as pleasant or intense is largely influenced by environment, cultural background, learning, and health (Mantel et al., 2021; Oleszkiewicz et al., 2020). Remarkably, the same odorous molecule may evoke an olfactory percept in most healthy people yet go completely unnoticed by others. This phenomenon, in which a person with an otherwise healthy sense of smell cannot detect a particular odorous molecule or a group of molecules is called specific anosmia (Hernandez et al., 2023), and is, at least partially, genetically determined (Wysocki & Beauchamp, 1984). Although humans have almost 400 functional genes expressing olfactory receptor neurons (Menashe et al., 2003; Niimura & Nei, 2006), the exact repertoire of expressed olfactory receptor genes differs from person to person (Gilad & Lancet, 2003; Keller et al., 2012; Menashe et al., 2003; Verbeurg et al., 2014), contributing to the inter-individual variability in olfactory perception.

Specific anosmia is a common and non-pathological phenomenon (Schäfer et al., 2021). Prediction of specific anosmia prevalence suggests that if a person was tested with 20 different odorants, the chance of being specifically anosmic to at least one of them is above 50%. When the number of odorants rises to 100, more than 98% of people will exhibit specific anosmia to at least one of the odorants (Croy et al., 2015). The rate of specific anosmia varies across different odorous molecules and is correlated with molecular weights of the odorants, with more people being specifically anosmic to heavier odorous molecules potentially due to more difficult passage of heavy molecules through the nasal mucosa (Croy et al., 2015). Finally, specific anosmia frequency may change throughout life – pre-school children exhibit specific anosmia towards non-steroid odorants more often than adolescents (Zou et al., 2020).

The human olfactory system is subject to dynamic changes throughout lifetime and has high regenerative capacities (Durante et al., 2020; Witt, 2020). This is possible due to the ongoing neurogenesis at the peripheral (and possibly also central) levels of the olfactory system. In the periphery, older olfactory receptor neurons are continuously replaced by novel neurons which mature from horizontal and globose basal cells located in the olfactory mucosa (Schwob et al., 2017). This constant turnover of novel olfactory receptor neurons allows to sustain high level of olfactory sensitivity until the 5th decade of life (Oleszkiewicz et al., 2019), when olfaction starts deteriorating due to age-related reduction of olfactory mucus and metaplastic conversion of the olfactory epithelium into respiratory epithelium (Kovacs, 2004; Shirai et al., 2023). The adult neurogenesis has also been reported in the human olfactory bulb, although its strength is reduced compared to rodents and non-primates (van Strien et al., 2011). Specifically, adult-born neurons are integrated into the olfactory bulb structure after migrating from the subventricular zone

through the rostral migratory stream (Bédard & Parent, 2004; Curtis et al., 2007; Lötsch et al., 2014).

The neuroplasticity of the olfactory system might be triggered by repeated exposure to odors. Rodent models show that olfactory stimulation contributes to the expression of anti-apoptotic genes what enhances survival of olfactory receptor neurons (Kim et al., 2015; Watt et al., 2004) as well as supports the survival of neurons located in the olfactory bulb and piriform cortex (Shapiro et al., 2007; Veyrac et al., 2009). Therefore, environmental changes such as increased presence of odors might contribute to regeneration and fine-tuning of the olfactory system. This principle of olfactory plasticity has been applied to the clinical otorhinolaryngological settings to design smell rehabilitation protocols. Regular exposure to odors, known as olfactory training (OT), has been proposed and proven effective as a tool to rehabilitate the sense of smell in people with olfactory dysfunction of different etiologies (Huang et al., 2021; Hummel et al., 2009; Kattar et al., 2021; Sorokowska et al., 2017). Following OT, participants have been reported to exhibit increased olfactory mucosa's electrophysiological responsiveness to olfactory stimuli (Hummel et al., 2018), increased olfactory bulb volume (Mahmut et al., 2020; Negoias et al., 2017), and increased functional connectivity within the olfactory brain network (Hosseini et al., 2020; Kollndorfer et al., 2015).

Compared to olfactory dysfunction treatment, the effects of OT on specific anosmia were not extensively investigated, most likely due to its non-pathological nature and challenging recruitment of specifically anosmic individuals to research studies. However, verifying how OT affects olfaction in specifically anosmic individuals may shed new light on the boundaries of the olfactory system plasticity. Specifically, results of the OT studies in people with olfactory dysfunction indicate that the olfactory system can regenerate following an infection or an injury (Delgado; Lima et al., 2024) but how this applies to individuals with a healthy sense of smell remains elusive. While OT has been investigated in healthy children and elderly people and reported to improve selected olfactory function in these age groups (Mahmut et al., 2021; Mori et al., 2015; Oleszkiewicz et al., 2021; Wegener et al., 2018), both these populations are prone to experience age-related changes in olfactory abilities. On the other hand, smell training in young healthy adults often uses training procedures activating higher order cognitive functions (e.g., working memory) during the exposure to odors (Al Aïn et al., 2019; Morquecho-Campos et al., 2019; Olofsson et al., 2020), making it difficult to disentangle the effects of olfactory stimulation from those arising from cognitive training (Pieniak et al., 2022). Studying specific anosmia offers a unique lens to examine OT-triggered olfactory plasticity in healthy people without such cognitive confounds.

Several studies have already investigated the effects of olfactory exposure on specific anosmia. People with a specific anosmia towards androstenone (a steroid present in human body secretions) who were regularly exposed to it for a period of 1–6 weeks, were subsequently reported to acquire perception of androstenone (Mörlein et al., 2013; Wysocki et al., 1989). This mechanism of gaining sensitivity to androstenone involves both peripheral and central processes as stimulating only one nostril with this compound leads to bilateral increase

in androstenone sensitivity (Mainland et al., 2002). The similar pattern was observed for other odorous molecules. Croy et al. reported that 25 people who were specifically anosmic to either isovaleric acid, pentadecanolide, cedrylmethylether, lylal or muscone, increased sensitivity towards the odorant they were specifically anosmic to after approximately 3 months of OT with that odorant (Croy et al., 2015). While these findings are based on relatively small samples, they indicate that the olfactory system of healthy adults with specific anosmia adapts to changes in the environment what leads to acquisition of new olfactory percepts. However, whether these effects are long-lasting – as it has been demonstrated for OT effects in people with an olfactory dysfunction (Konstantinidis et al., 2016; Pieniak et al., 2023) – and exceed the period of systematic olfactory recovery remains currently unknown. Examining the stability of OT effects on specific anosmia is needed, for one to verify if the underlying OT mechanism is the same as the one responsible for OT effects in people with olfactory dysfunction, and to test the limits of olfactory plasticity in humans.

The present study investigated the effects of OT on specific anosmia in a large sample of participants as well as test stability of the OT effects. Based on the previous research (Croy et al., 2015; Wysocki et al., 1989), we hypothesized that OT would increase sensitivity to odors in people who were specifically anosmic to them (i.e., who were not able to these odors at baseline). Additionally, we aimed to replicate previous findings on the high prevalence of specific anosmia, and the positive association between the rate of specific anosmia and the odorant's molecular weight using four different odorous molecules (androstenone, bacdanol, benzyl salicylate, maltol). Finally, we verified if specific anosmia is indeed a non-pathological phenomenon by relating it to participants' well-being and overall satisfaction with life.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Ethical statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethical Review Board at the Carl Gustav Carus Faculty of Medicine, Dresden University of Technology (application number EK67022018). All participants provided written consent after being informed in detail about the aims and procedure of the study. Volunteers received moderate financial compensation for their participation. The data presented here comes from a larger project and results unrelated to this study aim were presented elsewhere (Gillmeister et al., 2025).

2.2. Participants

Healthy adult participants were recruited via advertisements, leaflets, and social media. A total of 335 participants (206 women) aged between 18 and 52 years ($M = 27.1$, $SD = 7.2$ years) participated in the screening part of the study. Of these, 77 participants ($M = 26.9$, $SD = 7.2$, range 18–51 years; 41 women) completed approximately 2 months of olfactory training. Inclusion criterion for the study was a healthy sense

of smell as determined by an odor identification test (Oleszkiewicz et al., 2019; Sorokowska et al., 2019). No a priori power analysis was conducted, and the final sample size was determined by time constraints and feasibility.

2.3. Methods

2.3.1. Olfactory testing

Odor identification tests were used to assess participants' olfactory abilities. Odors were presented in felt-tip pens ("Sniffin' Sticks", Burghart, Holm, Germany; Hummel et al., 1997) and in each trial participant was asked to identify an odor from a list of 4 descriptors (1 target, 3 distractors). In the first steps, all participants were screened with the Q-Sticks test, comprising three odors (cloves, coffee, rose) (Sorokowska et al., 2019). Three correct identifications indicated intact olfactory functions. If a participant misidentified at least one of the three odors, 16-items Sniffin' Sticks identification test was conducted, in which at least 12 correct responses indicated normal olfactory function (Hummel et al., 1997; Oleszkiewicz et al., 2019).

2.3.2. Specific anosmia assessment

Participants were screened for specific anosmia towards four different molecules: androsterone (5 α -androst-16-en-3-one), bacdanol (2-Ethyl-4-(2,2,3-trimethylcyclopent-3-enyl-1)-2-buten-1-ol), benzyl salicylate (Benzyl 2-hydroxybenzoate), and maltol (3-hydrox-2-methyl-4-pyrone). These molecules were chosen because for all of them specific anosmia has been previously reported and they differ in molecular weight (Croy et al., 2015; Wysocki et al., 1989; Zou et al., 2020). Each molecule was diluted in propylene glycol. For androstenone and bacdanol, 6 dilutions were prepared (androstenone: 50 μ g/g, 5 μ g/g, .5 μ g/g, .05 μ g/g, .005 μ g/g, .0005 μ g/g; bacdanol: from 1:10² to 1:10⁷ with each consecutive dilution containing 10 times less odorant than the previous one). For benzyl salicylate and maltol, 7 dilutions were prepared ranging from 1:10² to 1:10⁸ with each consecutive dilution containing 10 times less odorant than the previous one. Dilutions were stored in 40 ml brown-glass jars and renewed every two months.

To assess specific anosmia, participants underwent odorant detection threshold tests, which indicate how sensitive an individual is towards an odorant. For each odorant, the procedure started with the lowest concentration. During each trial, participants were presented with the target odorant and two visually identical blank samples containing propylene glycol. Their task was to select the sample containing the target odorant. In case of an incorrect answer, the procedure was repeated with a higher concentration of the odorant. When participants provided a correct answer twice in a row for the same concentration, according to the reverse staircase procedure the lower concentrations of the odorant were presented until the first mistake occurred. Subsequently, participants were presented again with increasingly higher concentrations of the odorant until they correctly identified it on two consecutive trials. The detection threshold assessment finished after three turning points and the mean of the last two points was used as the detection threshold score (ranging from 1 to 6 for androstenone and bacdanol, and from 1 to 7 for

benzyl salicylate and maltol, with higher scores indicating greater olfactory sensitivity, i.e., lower detection threshold). Participants who could not detect the target odor at the highest concentration or scored between the highest and the second highest concentrations (scores 1 and 1.5) were considered specifically anosmic to that odorant.

2.3.3. Psychological measures

To assess participants' well-being, we used the 5-item WHO-5 Well-Being Index (Topp et al., 2015) where participants rate how frequently they felt different positive states in the last 2 weeks (e.g., 'I have felt cheerful in good spirits.'). Response options ranging from 'All the time' to 'At no time'.

To assess participants' satisfaction with life, the 5-item Satisfaction With Life Scale (Diener et al., 1985) was used. In this scale, participants rate how well different statements describe their life (e.g., 'In most ways my life is close to my ideal.') using a scale ranging from 1 ('Strongly disagree') to 7 ('Strongly agree').

To assess how important the sense of smell is for the participants, we used the 20-item Individual Significance of Olfaction Questionnaire (ISOQ; Croy et al., 2010). ISOQ assesses how important the sense of smell is for a participant across three domains: associations of odors with memories and emotions (e.g., 'Certain smells immediately activate numerous memories.'), applications of the sense of smell in daily activities (e.g., 'I smell foods to find out whether it is spoiled or not.'), and consequences of olfactory perception for one's behavior (e.g., 'When I don't like the smell of a shampoo, I don't buy it.'). Additionally, two items measure aggravation tendency (e.g., 'Without my sense of smell, life would be worthless.'). Participants rate the items on a scale from 1 ('I totally disagree') to 4 ('I totally agree').

2.3.4. Olfactory training

Participants with specific anosmia were asked to participate in olfactory training. Seventy-two participants ($M_{\text{age}} = 27$, $SD = 7.26$, range 18–51 years; 39 women) were equipped with four brown-glass jars containing androstenone, bacdanol, benzyl salicylate, and maltol. Five participants specifically anosmic to androstenone ($M_{\text{age}} = 24.8$, $SD = 4.12$, range 18–31 years; 2 women) received training sets with bacdanol, benzyl salicylate, and maltol only, to verify if their androstenone sensitivity might be increased without being exposed to it (their data regarding androstenone sensitivity were reported in Gillmeister et al., 2025).

To prevent spilling cotton balls were added to the jars so that they were soaked with the odorous solutions. During each training session, participants sniffed the content of each jar twice, each time for 20 s (Pieniak et al., 2022). Training sessions were tracked in a training diary where participants rated intensity of the odorants on a scale ranging from 0 to 10 on a weekly basis to later ensure the training was conducted. This method is commonly used in OT research to increase participant's engagement in OT and maximize compliance (Chao et al., 2022; Haehner et al., 2013). The intensity ratings were not used in any analyses. The training lasted approximately 2 months ($M = 60$ days, $SD = 9$ days, range: 43–99 days).

2.4. Procedure

In the first phase of the study, all participants had their sense of smell evaluated with odor identification tests to ensure they have healthy sense of smell (i.e., normosmia; Hernandez et al., 2023) and do not experience any qualitative/quantitative alterations of olfactory perception. Subsequently, normosmic participants were screened towards specific anosmia with all four odorant detection threshold tests. Participants with at least one specific anosmia were invited to participate in olfactory training. Following olfactory training, participants' odorant detection thresholds were measured again.

2.5. Statistical approach

All the analyses were conducted with R, with the significance level set to $\alpha = .05$. The changes in odorant detection thresholds between pre- and post-OT were verified by Wilcoxon signed rank test, with Wilcoxon method of handling zeros. We did not adjust p -values in these tests because each odorant had a pre-specified hypothesis of OT-related improvement, defined before data collection and analysis. For the longitudinal follow-up (three appointments), we first used the Friedman test. Subsequently, Wilcoxon signed rank test was used for the Bonferroni-corrected post hoc analyses to control for Type I error inflation due to pairwise comparisons. For the Wilcoxon signed rank test we estimated the rank biserial correlation (r) as the indicator of the effect size. It should be noted that in the context of specific anosmia where participants start at minimal values and the direction of change is unidimensional (participants can only improve or stay at the same level), the rank biserial correlation value might be inflated, especially for comparisons involving small sample size (<10). Between-group differences in age, psychological well-being and importance of olfaction between people with and without a specific anosmia were verified with independent samples t -test. Associations between psychological functioning and the number of odorants participants were specifically anosmic to, were verified using Spearman correlation.

3. Results

3.1. Rate of specific anosmia

In the entire sample of 335 participants, 46.6% ($n = 156$) of participants exhibited a specific anosmia towards at least one of the four tested odorants. The rate of specific anosmia for each of the odorants were: 30.7% for androstenone, 13.7% for benzyl salicylate, 11.9% for bacdanol, and 3.3% for maltol. The rate of specific anosmia exhibited a nearly linear relationship with the odorants' molecular weight, with more participants being specifically anosmic to heavier odorants (Fig. 1A). Participants with at least one specific anosmia did not differ from participants without specific anosmia regarding both age ($t = .53$, $df = 333$, $p = .599$) and gender distribution ($\chi^2 = 1.49$, $df = 1$, $p = .222$).

In the set of the four odorants used, the specific anosmia appeared to be a rather isolated phenomenon. More than 75%

Fig. 1 – (A) There is a linear relationship between the molecular weight of an odorant and the rate of people who are specifically anosmic towards it. (B) The Venn diagram demonstrates that most of the participants with a specific anosmia are specifically anosmic to only one of the four odorants. Specific anosmia towards more than one odorant is less frequent.

of people with a specific anosmia were specifically anosmic to only one of the four odorants. Only 7 out of 156 participants (4.5%) were specifically anosmic to 3 odorants, and none of the participants was specifically anosmic to all four odorants. Fig. 1B depicts the exact numbers and rates of specific anosmia towards one or more odorants.

3.2. Presence of specific anosmia and well-being

Participants with at least one specific anosmia ($n = 156$) and without a specific anosmia ($n = 179$) declared the same level of well-being ($t = .68$, $df = 333$, $p = .498$) and satisfaction with life ($t = .16$, $df = 333$, $p = .874$). There was also no correlation between the number of odorants a person is specifically anosmic to and their well-being (Spearman's $\rho = -.06$, $p = .308$) and life satisfaction (Spearman's $\rho = -.06$, $p = .308$).

Participants with at least one specific anosmia and without a specific anosmia differed in scores of the 'Consequence' subscale of the Individual Significance of Olfaction Questionnaire. Specifically, the participants without a specific anosmia ($M = 11.34$, $SD = 2.55$) declared that their daily behaviors and decisions are more influenced by smells than the participants with at least one specific anosmia ($M = 10.68$, $SD = 2.2$; $t = 2.45$,

$df = 323$, $p = .015$). The scores in the 'Application', 'Association' and 'Aggravation' subscales as well as the total scores did not differ between groups (all $t \geq 1.63$, all $p \geq .103$). There was a small, negative correlation between the number of odorants participants were specifically anosmic to, and their total ISOQ scores (Spearman's $\rho = -.13$, $p = .022$), and 'Consequence' subscale scores (Spearman's $\rho = -.17$, $p = .002$). There was no correlation between the scores in the 'Application', 'Association' and 'Aggravation' subscales, and the number of odorants participants were specifically anosmic to (all Spearman's $\rho \geq -.10$, all $p \geq .082$).

3.3. The effect of olfactory training on specific anosmia

In participants with specific anosmia, we observed a statistically significant increase in olfactory sensitivity (i.e., lower detection threshold) towards androstenone ($n = 68$; $Z = -6.70$, $p < .001$, $r = -1$), benzyl salicylate ($n = 12$; $Z = -2.81$, $p = .005$, $r = -.95$), and bacdanol ($n = 11$; $Z = -2.81$, $p = .005$, $r = -1$). In the case of the three participants with specific anosmia towards maltol, two of them exhibited an increase in their sensitivity (i.e., lower detection threshold), whereas one person did not ($Z = -1.34$, $p = .180$, $r = -1$).

Participants who were able to perceive androstenone ($n = 4$) and bacdanol ($n = 66$) before OT, did not exhibit change in their sensitivity towards these odorant (androstenone: $Z = -1.34$, $p = .180$, $r = -1$, bacdanol: $Z = -1.50$, $p = .133$, $r = -.22$). For participants with intact perception of benzyl salicylate ($n = 65$) we observed increase in olfactory sensitivity (i.e., lower detection threshold) following OT ($Z = -1.97$, $p = .048$, $r = -.31$), while participants who were able to detect maltol ($n = 74$) showed a trend-level increase in their olfactory sensitivity (i.e., lower detection threshold; $Z = -1.73$, $p = .083$, $r = -.27$). All these results are presented in Fig. 2.

3.4. Stability of the olfactory training effects

Approximately 19 months after OT completion ($M = 18.9$, $SD = 1.3$, range 16–20 months), 10 participants who were at baseline specifically anosmic towards androstenone came back for a follow-up measurement. We observed that these participants exhibited statistically significant differences in their androstenone sensitivity throughout the study period ($\chi^2 = 15.8$, $df = 2$, $p < .001$, Kendall's $W = .79$; Fig. 3). Bonferroni-corrected post hoc tests demonstrated that these participants had increased androstenone sensitivity (i.e., lower detection threshold) after the OT ($p = .017$, $r = -.89$), but this increase was temporary and during the follow-up measurement the androstenone sensitivity was significantly lower than after the OT ($p = .047$, $r = .78$; the detection threshold increased). The androstenone sensitivity at baseline and during the follow-up did not significantly differ, suggesting that most participants again became specifically anosmic towards androstenone ($p = .267$, $r = -.63$).

4. Discussion

The primary aim of the study was to verify the effects of OT on specific anosmia and, to the best of our knowledge, for the first

Fig. 2 – Changes in the olfactory sensitivity towards four different odorous molecules: (A) androstenone, (B) bacdanol, (C) benzyl salicylate, and (D) maltol. Most participants demonstrated an increase in their sensitivity towards odorants they were specifically anosmic to. Sensitivity towards odorants which were perceived normally at baseline did not change (androstenone, bacdanol) or slightly increased (benzyl salicylate, maltol).

Note. OT – olfactory training, r – rank–biserial correlation. Higher scores indicate higher level of olfactory sensitivity, i.e., lower detection threshold. The number of participants is different for androstenone sensitivity as 5 participants received training set without androstenone. Data from these participants were reported elsewhere. The effect size (r) might be inflated due to unidimensional changes of olfactory sensitivity scores, especially in comparisons involving small samples.

Fig. 3 – Sensitivity to androstenone increased after olfactory training but this effect was not stable over time. Most of the tested participants ($n = 10$) exhibited specific anosmia towards androstenone both at the baseline and during the follow-up period.

Note. OT – olfactory training, r – rank–biserial correlation. Higher scores indicate higher level of olfactory sensitivity, i.e., lower detection threshold. The effect size (r) might be inflated due to unidimensional changes of olfactory sensitivity scores.

time investigate the stability of these effects. Additionally, our goal was to replicate the previous findings on the high prevalence of specific anosmia and its association with molecular weight. Finally, we verified how specific anosmia relates to well-being, life satisfaction, and importance of the sense of smell.

Participants who were at baseline specifically anosmic to different odorous molecules, acquired sensitivity towards these odorants following OT. This effect was present for androstenone, benzyl salicylate, and bacdanol, as well as for two out of three cases of specific anosmia to maltol. These results obtained in a large sample of participants corroborate previous findings on the effects of olfactory stimulation on specific anosmia (Croy et al., 2015; Pause et al., 1999; Wysocki et al., 1989). The exact mechanism through which OT improves specific anosmia in humans awaits more in-depth investigation, however, both peripheral and central mechanisms are likely to contribute to this effect. Animal models demonstrate that olfactory stimulation promotes neurogenesis and survival of olfactory receptor neurons in the olfactory epithelium, especially of these subtypes which are responsive to the stimulating odorant (Avaro et al., 2022; van der Linden et al., 2020; Watt et al., 2004; Yusuf & Monahan, 2024). These processes are likely to be at least partially

modulated via top-down processes as olfactory stimulation of one nostril leads to bilateral increase in the volumes of both olfactory bulbs (Negoiias et al., 2017) and in sensitivity towards the stimulating odorant in both nostrils (Mainland et al., 2002). Therefore, it is plausible that at baseline the specifically anosmic individuals did not express required olfactory receptor neurons at all or in a quantity insufficient to evoke a response, but OT enhanced expression of novel receptors and adjusted their type to the novel olfactory environment.

Participants who were able to detect benzyl salicylate, bacdanol, and maltol at baseline exhibited less spectacular or marginal increase in their olfactory sensitivity following OT, even though all these odorants were included in the training set. This suggests that there are limits to supporting one's olfactory sensitivity – if a person can detect and perceive the odorant, the capacity for further increase is lower. Alternatively, the left-skewed distribution of the sensitivity scores in people with normal perception of the odorants might also indicate presence of a ceiling effect which hinders accurate estimation of the OT effects (Pieniak et al., 2024). However, complete control of a ceiling effect is challenging considering that odor detection threshold task would need to account for both heterogeneity of detection thresholds for different odorants and inter-individual differences in olfactory sensitivity due to age, health status, gender or geographical location (Cecchini et al., 2021; Leonardos et al., 1969; Oleszkiewicz et al., 2020; Ren et al., 2025; Sabiniewicz et al., 2023).

Data from the follow-up appointment demonstrate that the increase in androstenone sensitivity following OT is only transient. While most participants acquired perception of androstenone after 2 months of daily exposure to it, they lost this capacity after the training had been concluded. This effect supports the idea that changes of olfactory sensitivity in specific anosmia are triggered by shifts in the olfactory environment which in turn fine-tune the expression of olfactory receptor neurons towards detection of the novel olfactory inputs. However, once the novel odorants are not regularly present in the environment anymore, the composition of olfactory receptor neurons in the olfactory epithelium may return to a 'default' state determined by individual genetic factors (Wysocki & Beauchamp, 1984). The stability of OT effects on specific anosmia is therefore likely to overlap with the lifespan of olfactory receptor neurons born during the training period, i. e., from several weeks to several months (Avaro et al., 2022). Thus, the inability to perceive a specific odorant is a qualitatively different phenomenon from olfactory impairment as the rehabilitation of olfactory function via OT leads to broader and long-lasting effects in people who lost their sense of smell due to an infection or an injury (Konstantinidis et al., 2016; Mahmut, Uecker, et al., 2020; Oleszkiewicz et al., 2018, 2022).

There is a remaining question on how OT effects on specific anosmia depend on the inter-individual differences in genetically determined olfactory receptor expression. The role of genotype in olfactory perception was discussed particularly in the context of androstenone which (together with androstadienone) selectively activates the OR7D4 receptor (Keller et al., 2007) and OR7D4 polymorphism was linked to changes in androstenone perception (Lunde et al., 2012). However, it remains unknown how much the genetic factors contribute to the variability in specific OT effects on other odorants.

Additionally, even in the context of androstenone and OR7D4 the picture is far from complete – a recent study reported that androstenone activates 84 different olfactory receptors (Nishijima et al., 2025) what might play compensatory function and explains the null effect of OR7D4 polymorphism on androstenone sensitivity and intensity ratings which we observed in the present project (Gillmeister et al., 2025).

Apart from examining the effects of OT on specific anosmia, we confirmed that specific anosmia occurs frequently. While participants were only tested with four odorants, almost half of them demonstrated at least one specific anosmia. This prevalence of specific anosmia is odorant-dependent and most participants who were specifically anosmic were unable to perceive androstenone whereas other odorants were perceived by the majority of individuals, replicating previous reports of high frequency of androstenone-specific anosmia (Bremner et al., 2003). However, as we aimed to verify OT effects on specific anosmia, we used odorants that were previously reported to be non-detected by many people, therefore, the chances of finding specifically anosmic people were higher than if we had selected four random odorants. Additionally, all the estimates of specific anosmia prevalence are dependent on the operationalization of the specific anosmia. We used the lowest score in a 3-alternatives forced choice threshold test and this approach may be detecting more people with specific anosmia than other methods, such as multiple repetitions of a yes-no forced choice task (Bremner et al., 2003). Regardless of whether the used method detects 'true' specific anosmia or only severe specific hyposmia, the obtained results clearly demonstrate that people with a healthy sense of smell might be unable to perceive selected odorants in a functional way, contributing to the inter-individual variability in olfactory perception (Mantel et al., 2021).

The rate of specific anosmia for each of the tested odorants was positively related to the odorant's molecular weight. While these results cannot be generalized due to very small number of odorants used in the study, the observed pattern is consistent with previous findings (Amoore, 1977; Croy et al., 2015). Several mechanisms explaining this relationship have been proposed. Heavier molecules might be less volatile and less likely to pass through the olfactory mucosa (Croy et al., 2015) or their bigger and more complex structure hinders binding to the olfactory receptors (Amoore, 1964; Araneda et al., 2000). The same mechanisms have been proposed as explanations for odorant-specific age-related decline in olfactory sensitivity. Specifically, as the heavier molecules may require more specific olfactory receptors, their perception may be impaired by age-related degeneration of the olfactory mucosa (Fitzek et al., 2022), whereas light molecules requiring less selective olfactory receptors might remain perceivable despite damages to the olfactory epithelium (Sinding et al., 2014). However, in the context of age-related olfactory decline, the link between olfactory sensitivity and molecular weight diminishes when detection thresholds are measured for greater number of odorants (Sabiniewicz et al., 2023), urging further research on the molecular determinants of olfactory sensitivity and specific anosmia prevalence, with more odorants included. The future attempts to predict which odorants people are more often specifically anosmic to will

greatly benefit from using machine learning algorithms based on high quality experimental data from human studies as well as accurate characterization of odorants' molecular features (Mayhew et al., 2022). Such an approach has been successfully employed in predicting which molecules are odorous and odorless based on molecular transport features such as the boiling point, vapor pressure, hydrophilicity, and lipophilicity (Mayhew et al., 2022).

In the present study, participants who showed a specific anosmia towards at least one of the odorants did not differ in terms of well-being and life satisfaction from people who were able to perceive all the tested smells, supporting previous claims that specific anosmia is a non-pathological phenomenon (Hernandez et al., 2023). Interestingly, participants with specific anosmia differed in self-rated levels of importance of their sense of smell in daily functioning, particularly regarding consequences of olfactory experiences on behavior. Considering that most of the specifically anosmic participants in our study were unable to perceive androstenone and the 'Consequence' subscale of the Individual Significance of Olfaction Questionnaire includes items about perception of smells in the social context ('If my partner has a nasty smell, I avoid kissing him.', 'When there is a nasty smell in the office/apartment of a colleague, I leave the room as soon as possible. '), it is possible that the observed effect (albeit small) is driven by the altered perception of body odors of other people. Therefore, specific anosmia might not negatively impact the general life-quality but may alter social functioning. The latter has been recently demonstrated by Friesen et al. who reported a small positive correlation between detection of androstenone and political preference for social order (Friesen et al., 2020). On the other hand, specific anosmia towards 3-hydroxy-3-methylhexanoic acid (an odorous molecule present in axillary secretions) did not interfere with social functioning (Sorokowska et al., 2022) demonstrating that the impact of specific anosmia towards body odor components requires further investigations.

The present study is limited by several factors. First, we tested the OT effects on sensitivity towards four odorous molecules and while the results followed a similar pattern for all molecules and were in line with previous reports (Croy et al., 2015), we cannot directly transfer these findings to molecules with different physico-chemical molecular features. It remains possible that there are exceptions where OT does not increase sensitivity towards an odor someone is specifically anosmic to. Additionally, the follow-up examination included only 10 participants, limiting statistical power, and we tested only androstenone sensitivity. Although 9 out of 10 participants returned to scores in the range of specific anosmia, similar investigations with different odorous molecules are needed before generalizing our findings. Finally, in the current study, changes in sensitivity towards odors participants were able to perceive at baseline served as a within-person control condition but a passive control group which did not engage in any form of training was not included to maximize the number of participants conducting OT. Future studies including a longitudinal observation of olfactory sensitivity in individuals

with specific anosmia will broaden our understanding of physiological fluctuations not caused by OT.

In conclusion, we demonstrated that specific anosmia is a frequent phenomenon and does not influence life quality in general. Regular training enhances sensitivity towards previously undetected odorants, however, the effects typically disappear in healthy participants after the training is concluded.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Antonia Gillmeister: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Michał Pieniak:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Thomas Hummel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2025.08.012>.

Scientific transparency statement

DATA: All raw and processed data supporting this research are publicly available: <https://osf.io/gaw53/>

CODE: All analysis code supporting this research is publicly available: <https://osf.io/gaw53/>

MATERIALS: All study materials supporting this research are publicly available: <https://osf.io/gaw53/>

DESIGN: This article reports, for all studies, how the author (s) determined all sample sizes, all data exclusions, all data inclusion and exclusion criteria, and whether inclusion and exclusion criteria were established prior to data analysis.

PRE-REGISTRATION: No part of the study procedures was pre-registered in a time-stamped, institutional registry prior to the research being conducted. No part of the analysis plans

was pre-registered in a time-stamped, institutional registry prior to the research being conducted.

For full details, see the *Scientific Transparency Report* in the supplementary data to the online version of this article.

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